

ORDER ESTIMATION FOR MULTIVARIATE MIXTURE REGRESSION MODELS

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Abstract

In this paper, we study the problem of jointly selecting the number of components and explanatory variables for multivariate mixture regression models. In practice, the selection model using the Akaike Information Criterion AIC is not satisfactory, as it can lead to an overestimation of the number of components and the number of explanatory variables. To improve selection, Naik et al. (2007) developed a new criterion based on Akaike's technique, the Mixture Regression Criterion MRC for the simultaneous determination of the number of components and explanatory variables for univariate mixture regression models. We propose a generalization of the criterion MRC for multivariate mixture regression models. The performance of the new criterion is validated on simulated data by comparing it to the Akaike criterion AIC and the Schwarz criterion BIC .

Keywords: Model Selection, Information Criteria, Criterion MRC , Multivariate Mixture Regression Models.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mixture regression models combine several regression models to model different sub-populations in relation to the observed data. Each sub-population is modeled by a different regression model whose weight corresponds to the proportion of this sub-population in the total population. Mixture regression models are useful for modeling situations where the relationships between explanatory variables may vary between sub-populations. They are also useful for detecting heterogeneous sub-populations with different relationships between explanatory variables. These models first appeared in the economic literature as "switching regression" (Quandt, 1972; Quandt et al., 1978) [13, 14] and have been widely used to explore the source of heterogeneity when groups of individuals respond differently to a predictor. Over the last decades, mixture regression models have been used in a large number of applications in a wide range of scientific disciplines. These models are commonly used in econometrics, biostatistics, and social sciences.

Selecting the appropriate order in multivariate mixture regression models typically involves determining the number of components in the mixture and the number of explanatory variables in each regression model.

The classical model selection criterion AIC (Akaike, 1973) [1] may not yield satisfactory results in selecting both the number of components and explanatory variables, particularly when the sample size is small, it leads to an over estimation of the number of components and the number of variables for mixture regression models. To overcome this problem, Naik et al. [12] developed the Mixture Regression Criterion MRC for the simultaneous determination of the number of components and explanatory variables for univariate mixture regression models, based on the log-likelihood of complete data and asymmetric divergence of Kullback [8] between the true and fitted approximating models. Using the same technique, we derive a new criterion, denoted MRC_v (*vector MRC*), which generalizes the MRC criterion to multivariate mixture regression models.

The paper is organized as follows. We present in Section 2 the multivariate mixture regression model and parameter estimation using the EM algorithm. In Section 3, we derive the criterion MRC_v . In Section 4, we highlight the performance of our criterion MRC_v compared to the criteria AIC and BIC on simulated data from multivariate gaussian mixture regression models.

1. Multivariate gaussian mixture regression models

Let y be a m -dimensional response variable and a p -dimensional explanatory variable x .

A multivariate gaussian mixture regression model consists of expressing y as a function of x as follows

$$y = \begin{cases} \beta'_1 x + \epsilon_1 & \text{with the probability } \alpha_1 \\ \beta'_2 x + \epsilon_2 & \text{with the probability } \alpha_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \beta'_k x + \epsilon_k & \text{with the probability } \alpha_k \end{cases}$$

such that for $j = 1, \dots, k$, $0 < \alpha_j \leq 1$ and $\sum_{j=1}^k \alpha_j = 1$, β_j is the $p \times m$ matrix of regression coefficients, and ϵ_j is the m – dimensional random error, we suppose that ϵ_j follows a gaussian distribution with mean 0 and covariance matrix Σ_j , $\epsilon_j \sim \mathcal{N}_m(0, \Sigma_j)$.

Let $\phi = \{(\alpha_j, \beta_j, \Sigma_j), j = 1, \dots, k\}$ be the set of parameters. The conditional density of y given x is

$$f(y; x, \phi) = \sum_{j=1}^k \alpha_j f_j(y; x, \beta_j, \Sigma_j) \tag{1}$$

k is the number of model components and f_j is the density function of the gaussian distribution of dimension m with mean $\beta'_j x$ and covariance matrix Σ_j .

$$f_j(y; x, \beta_j, \Sigma_j) = (2\pi)^{-\frac{m}{2}} (\det(\Sigma_j))^{-\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2} (y - \beta'_j x)' \Sigma_j^{-1} (y - \beta'_j x)\right\}$$

Let $\{(y_1, x_1), \dots, (y_n, x_n)\}$ be an independent observed sample from the model (1), the log-likelihood function is

$$L(\phi; Y, X) = \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^k \alpha_j f_j(y_i; x_i, \beta_j, \Sigma_j) \right\} \quad (2)$$

where $Y = (y_1, \dots, y_n)'$ and $X = (x_1, \dots, x_n)'$.

The maximum likelihood estimator for the parameters ϕ is

$$\hat{\phi} = \underset{\phi}{\operatorname{argmax}} \{L(\phi; Y, X)\} \quad (3)$$

However, no explicit solution is available due to the complex expression of $L(\phi; Y, X)$. We use the *EM* (Expectation-Maximization) algorithm (Dempster et al, 1977) [4] to solve this problem in which we introduce a latent variable Z of dimension $n \times k$ such that

$$z_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (y_i, x_i) \text{ arises from the } j^{\text{th}} \text{ component} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

We put $z_i = (z_{i1}, \dots, z_{ik})$, the completed data became $((y_i, x_i, z_i), i = 1, \dots, n)$. The log-likelihood function for the completed data is

$$\begin{aligned} L_c(\phi; Y, X, Z) &= \log \prod_{i=1}^n \prod_{j=1}^k \{ \alpha_j f_j(y_i; x_i, \beta_j, \Sigma_j) \}^{z_{ij}} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^k z_{ij} \{ \log \alpha_j + \log f_j(y_i; x_i, \beta_j, \Sigma_j) \} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The EM algorithm is an iterative estimation algorithm, starting with an initial parameter value $\phi^{(0)}$. For each iteration, we calculate the new parameters $\phi^{(q+1)}$ from those of the previous iteration $\phi^{(q)}$.

E step:

Calculate the expectation of L_c conditional on the observed data and the current parameter. We obtain

$$Q(\phi, \phi^{(q)}) = E(L_c / Y, X, \phi^{(q)}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^k \tau_{ij}^{(q)} \{ \log \alpha_j + \log f_j(y_i; x_i, \beta_j, \Sigma_j) \}$$

where $\tau_{ij}^{(q)} = E(z_{ij} / y_i, x_i, \phi^{(q)}) = P(z_{ij} = 1 / y_i, x_i, \phi^{(q)})$

by the Bayes's formula, we have

$$\tau_{ij}^{(q)} = \frac{\alpha_j^{(q)} f_j(y_i; x_i, \beta_j^{(q)}, \Sigma_j^{(q)})}{\sum_{j=1}^k \alpha_j^{(q)} f_j(y_i; x_i, \beta_j^{(q)}, \Sigma_j^{(q)})} \quad (5)$$

M step:

Compute $\phi^{(q+1)}$ maximizing $Q(\phi, \phi^{(q)})$ with respect to ϕ . We obtain the following updates

$$\alpha_j^{(q+1)} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\tau_{ij}^{(q)}}{n}$$

$$\beta_j^{(q+1)} = (\tilde{X}_j^{(q)'} \tilde{X}_j^{(q)})^{-1} \tilde{X}_j^{(q)'} \tilde{Y}_j^{(q)}$$

$$\Sigma_j^{(q+1)} = \frac{\tilde{Y}_j^{(q)'} (I - \tilde{H}_j^{(q)}) \tilde{Y}_j^{(q)}}{tr(W_j^{(q)})}$$

where $W_j^{(q)} = diag(\tau_j^{(q)})$, $\tau_j^{(q)} = (\tau_{1j}^{(q)}, \dots, \tau_{nj}^{(q)})'$, $\tilde{Y}_j^{(q)} = (W_j^{(q)})^{1/2} Y$

$\tilde{X}_j^{(q)} = (W_j^{(q)})^{1/2} X$ and $\tilde{H}_j^{(q)} = \tilde{X}_j^{(q)} (\tilde{X}_j^{(q)'} \tilde{X}_j^{(q)})^{-1} \tilde{X}_j^{(q)'}$

We denote $\hat{\alpha}_1, \dots, \hat{\alpha}_k, \hat{\beta}_1, \dots, \hat{\beta}_k, \hat{\Sigma}_1, \dots, \hat{\Sigma}_k$ the estimators obtained by the EM algorithm (we fix a stop threshold for the iterations).

3. Estimating the number of components and variables in multivariate gaussian mixture regression models

Our objective is the joint selection of the number of components and explanatory variables in multivariate gaussian mixture regression models.

3.1. The criterion MRC for univariate gaussian mixture regression models

In a univariate gaussian mixture regression model, the conditional density of the response variable y as a function of the explanatory variable x is written as follows

$$f(y; x, \phi) = \sum_{j=1}^k \alpha_j f_j(y; x, \beta_j, \sigma_j^2)$$

where $\phi = \{(\alpha_j, \beta_j, \sigma_j^2), j = 1, \dots, k\}$ is the set of parameters such that

$0 < \alpha_j \leq 1$ and $\sum_{j=1}^k \alpha_j = 1$, k is the number of model components, β_j is a $p \times 1$ parameter vector, x is a fixed $p \times 1$ vector of explanatory variables and f_j is the density function of the univariate gaussian distribution with mean $x' \beta_j$ and variance σ_j^2 . The parameters are estimated by the EM algorithm

$$\hat{\alpha}_j = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\hat{t}_{ij}}{n}$$

$$\hat{\beta}_j = (\hat{X}_j' \hat{X}_j)^{-1} \hat{X}_j' \hat{Y}_j$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_j^2 = \frac{\hat{Y}_j' (I - \hat{H}_j) \hat{Y}_j}{tr(\hat{W}_j)}$$

where $\widehat{W}_j = \text{diag}(\hat{t}_j)$, $\hat{t}_j = (\hat{t}_{1j}, \dots, \hat{t}_{nj})'$, $\hat{Y}_j = (\widehat{W}_j)^{1/2} Y$, $\hat{X}_j = (\widehat{W}_j)^{1/2} X$
and $\hat{H}_j = \hat{X}_j(\hat{X}_j' \hat{X}_j)^{-1} \hat{X}_j'$

For the simultaneous determination of the unknown number of components k° and the unknown number p° of explanatory variables for a univariate gaussian mixture regression model, Naik et al. [12] developed the Mixture Regression Criterion *MRC* based on the Kulback asymmetric divergence and the log-likelihood of complete data

$$MRC(k, p) = \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{n}_j \log(\hat{\sigma}_j^2) + \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{\hat{n}_j(\hat{n}_j + p_j)}{(\hat{n}_j - p_j - 2)} - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{n}_j \log(\hat{\alpha}_j)$$

with $p = (p_1, \dots, p_k)$, $\hat{n}_j = \text{tr}(\widehat{W}_j)$ and $p_j = \text{tr}(\hat{H}_j)$

$$(\hat{k}, \hat{p}) = \underset{1 \leq k \leq K, 1 \leq p_1, \dots, p_k \leq P}{\text{argmin}} \{MRC(k, p)\}$$

where K and P are sufficiently large such that $K \geq k^\circ$ and $P \geq \max\{p_j^\circ, j = 1, \dots, k^\circ\}$.

The criterion *MRC* is composed of three terms:

The first term measures the lack of fit, the second term imposes a penalty on the regression parameters and the third term penalizes the number of components.

We propose to extend their technique to multivariate gaussian mixture regression models by developing a more general criterion denoted *MRC_v*.

3.2. Extension of the criterion *MRC* for multivariate gaussian mixture regression models

Suppose that the density associated with the true model is

$$f^\circ(y; x^\circ, \phi^\circ) = \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \alpha_j^\circ f_j^\circ(y; x^\circ, \beta_j^\circ, \Sigma_j^\circ) \quad (6)$$

where $y \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $x^\circ \in \mathbb{R}^p$, $\phi^\circ = \{(\alpha_j^\circ, \beta_j^\circ, \Sigma_j^\circ), j = 1, \dots, k^\circ\}$ is the set of true model parameters such that $(0 < \alpha_j^\circ \leq 1$ and $\sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \alpha_j^\circ = 1)$, k° is the number of components of the true model and f_j° is the density function of the gaussian distribution of dimension m with mean $(\beta_j^\circ)'x^\circ$ and covariance matrix Σ_j° .

We assume that the class of candidate models, as defined by (1), includes the true model of order (k°, p°) . Under this assumption, the columns of X can be rearranged so that $X^\circ \beta_j^\circ = X \beta_j^*$ with $\beta_j^* = ((\beta_j^\circ)', (\beta_j^1)')'$ and β_j^1 is the null matrix of dimension $(p - p^\circ) \times m$,

for $j = 1, \dots, k^\circ$ when $p \geq p^\circ$. (Edward, J. et al., 1994) [6]

The candidate model has been fitted using the observed sample Y and the estimated parameters $\hat{\theta} = (\hat{\phi}, \hat{\tau})$ where $\hat{\tau} = (\hat{\tau}_1, \dots, \hat{\tau}_k)$ are obtained by the EM algorithm. Let $Y^* = (y_1^*, \dots, y_n^*)'$ be a sample associated with the true model and independent of Y , and we measure the goodness of fit by

$$I(\theta^\circ, \hat{\theta}(Y)) = E_{Y_{|\theta^\circ}} \{L_c^\circ(\phi^\circ; Z^*, Y^*, X) - L_c(\hat{\phi}(Y); \hat{\tau}(Y), Y^*, X)\} \quad (7)$$

where Z^* is an $n \times k^\circ$ matrix such that

$$z_{ij}^* = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (y_i^*, x_i) \text{ arises from the } j^{\text{th}} \text{ component} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$E_{Y_{|\theta^\circ}}$ denotes the expectation under the true model and $\theta^\circ = (\phi^\circ, \tau^\circ)$ where $\tau_{ij}^\circ = E(z_{ij}^*/y_i^*)$

We base the order estimation on the minimization of

$$E_{Y_{|\theta^\circ}} \{I(\theta^\circ, \hat{\theta}(Y))\} = E_{Y_{|\theta^\circ}} \left\{ E_{Y_{|\theta^\circ}} \{L_c^\circ(\phi^\circ; Z^*, Y^*, X)\} - E_{Y_{|\theta^\circ}} \{L_c(\hat{\phi}(Y); \hat{\tau}(Y), Y^*, X)\} \right\}$$

Considering only the terms that depend on the candidate model, the order estimation is obtained by minimizing $E_{Y_{|\theta^\circ}} \{E_{Y_{|\theta^\circ}} \{-L_c(\hat{\phi}(Y); \hat{\tau}(Y), Y^*, X)\}\}$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} L_c(\hat{\phi}(Y); \hat{\tau}(Y), Y^*, X) &= \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{\tau}_{ij} \{ \log \hat{\alpha}_j + \log f_j(y_i^*; x_i, \hat{\beta}_j, \hat{\Sigma}_j) \} \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{\tau}_{ij} \left\{ \log \hat{\alpha}_j - \frac{m}{2} \log(2\pi) \right\} \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{\tau}_{ij} \log(\det(\hat{\Sigma}_j)) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{\tau}_{ij} (y_i^* - \hat{\beta}_j' x)' \hat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} (y_i^* - \hat{\beta}_j' x) \end{aligned}$$

Then $L_c(\hat{\phi}(Y), \hat{\tau}(Y), Y^*, X) = \sum_{j=1}^k \text{tr}(\hat{W}_j) \log \hat{\alpha}_j - \frac{nm}{2} \log(2\pi)$

$$\begin{aligned} &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^k \text{tr}(\hat{W}_j) \log(\det(\hat{\Sigma}_j)) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^k \text{tr} \left[\hat{W}_j^{1/2} (Y^* - X\hat{\beta}_j) \hat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} (Y^* - X\hat{\beta}_j)' \hat{W}_j^{1/2} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

So

$$\begin{aligned}
 -2E_{Y_{|\theta}^*} \{L_c(\hat{\Phi}(Y), \hat{t}(Y), Y^*, X)\} &= -2 \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \text{tr}(\hat{W}_j) \log \hat{a}_j + nm \log(2\pi) \\
 &\quad + \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \text{tr}(\hat{W}_j) \log(\det(\hat{\Sigma}_j)) \\
 &\quad + E_{Y_{|\theta}^*} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^k \text{tr}[\hat{W}_j^{1/2} (Y^* - X\hat{\beta}_j) \hat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} (Y^* - X\hat{\beta}_j)' \hat{W}_j^{1/2}] \right\} \quad (9)
 \end{aligned}$$

We put $A = E_{Y_{|\theta}^*} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^k \text{tr}[\hat{W}_j^{1/2} (Y^* - X\hat{\beta}_j) \hat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} (Y^* - X\hat{\beta}_j)' \hat{W}_j^{1/2}] \right\}$

and $U_j^\circ = Y^* - X^\circ \beta_j^\circ = Y^* - X\beta_j^*$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Then } A &= E_{Y_{|\theta}^*} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^k \text{tr} \left[\hat{W}_j^{1/2} (X\beta_j^* + U_j^\circ - X\hat{\beta}_j) \hat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} \left[\hat{W}_j^{1/2} (X\beta_j^* + U_j^\circ - X\hat{\beta}_j) \right]' \right] \right\} \\
 &= E_{Y_{|\theta}^*} \left[\sum_{j=1}^k \text{tr} \{ \hat{X}_j (\beta_j^* - \hat{\beta}_j) \hat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} (\beta_j^* - \hat{\beta}_j)' \hat{X}_j' \} \right] + E_{Y_{|\theta}^*} \left[\sum_{j=1}^k \text{tr} \{ \hat{W}_j^{1/2} U_j^\circ \hat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} (U_j^\circ)' \hat{W}_j^{1/2} \} \right] \\
 &= E_{Y_{|\theta}^*} \left[\sum_{j=1}^k \text{tr} \{ \hat{X}_j (\beta_j^* - \hat{\beta}_j) \hat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} (\beta_j^* - \hat{\beta}_j)' \hat{X}_j' \} \right] + E_{Y_{|\theta}^*} \left[\sum_{j=1}^k \text{tr} \{ \hat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} (U_j^\circ)' \hat{W}_j (U_j^\circ) \} \right] \\
 &= \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \text{tr} \{ \hat{X}_j (\beta_j^* - \hat{\beta}_j) \hat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} (\beta_j^* - \hat{\beta}_j)' \hat{X}_j' \} + \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \text{tr} \{ \hat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} \text{tr}(\hat{W}_j) \Sigma_j^\circ \} \quad (10)
 \end{aligned}$$

So

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{Y_{|\theta}^*} \left\{ -2E_{Y_{|\theta}^*} \{L_c(\hat{\Phi}(Y), \hat{t}(Y), Y^*, X)\} \right\} &= E_{Y_{|\theta}^*} \left\{ -2 \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \text{tr}(\hat{W}_j) \hat{a}_j + nm \log(2\pi) \right\} \\
 &\quad + E_{Y_{|\theta}^*} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \text{tr}(\hat{W}_j) \log(\det(\hat{\Sigma}_j)) \right\} \\
 &\quad + E_{Y_{|\theta}^*} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \text{tr} \{ \hat{X}_j (\beta_j^* - \hat{\beta}_j) \hat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} (\beta_j^* - \hat{\beta}_j)' \hat{X}_j' \} \right\} \\
 &\quad + E_{Y_{|\theta}^*} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \text{tr}(\hat{W}_j) \text{tr}(\hat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} \Sigma_j^\circ) \right\} \quad (11)
 \end{aligned}$$

$\hat{\tau}_j$ is a consistent estimator of $\tau_j^\circ = (\tau_{1j}^\circ, \dots, \tau_{nj}^\circ)$ where $\tau_{ij}^\circ = E(z_{ij}^\circ/y_i, x_i)$ [15, 9, 12]

Consequently, we can consider $W_j^\circ = \text{diag}(\tau_j^\circ)$ and H_j° in the third and fourth terms of (11) instead of \widehat{W}_j and \widehat{H}_j respectively, where $H_j^\circ = X_j^\circ (X_j^{\circ'} X_j^\circ)^{-1} X_j^{\circ'}$ and $X_j^\circ = (W_j^\circ)^{1/2} X$ and to simplify further we assume that in the true model, the classes are disjoint such that the diagonal elements of W_j° are equal to either 1 or 0.

Furthermore, $\widehat{\Sigma}_j$ is asymptotically independent of $\widehat{\beta}_j$ and $n_j^\circ \widehat{\Sigma}_j$ is asymptotically distributed as $Wishart_m(\Sigma_j^\circ, n_j^\circ - p_j^\circ)$, and $E_{Y_{|\theta}^\circ}(\widehat{\Sigma}_j^{-1}) \approx d_j^\circ (\Sigma_j^\circ)^{-1}$ where $d_j^\circ = \frac{n_j^\circ}{n_j^\circ - (p_j^\circ + m + 1)}$ (Anderson, pp. 270, 290) [2]. Consequently

$$\begin{aligned}
 & E_{Y_{|\theta}^\circ} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \text{tr} \{ X_j^\circ (\beta_j^* - \widehat{\beta}_j) \widehat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} (\beta_j^* - \widehat{\beta}_j)' (X_j^\circ)' \} \right\} \\
 &= \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \left\{ \text{tr} \left[E_{Y_{|\theta}^\circ}(\widehat{\Sigma}_j^{-1}) E_{Y_{|\theta}^\circ} \left\{ (\beta_j^* - \widehat{\beta}_j)' (X_j^\circ)' X_j^\circ (\beta_j^* - \widehat{\beta}_j) \right\} \right] \right\} \\
 &\approx \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \left\{ \text{tr} \left[d_j^\circ (\Sigma_j^\circ)^{-1} E_{Y_{|\theta}^\circ} \left\{ (\beta_j^* - \widehat{\beta}_j)' (X_j^\circ)' X_j^\circ (\beta_j^* - \widehat{\beta}_j) \right\} \right] \right\} \\
 &= \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \left\{ d_j^\circ \text{tr} \left[E_{Y_{|\theta}^\circ} \left\{ (\Sigma_j^\circ)^{-1} (\beta_j^* - \widehat{\beta}_j)' (X_j^\circ)' X_j^\circ (\beta_j^* - \widehat{\beta}_j) \right\} \right] \right\} \\
 &= \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \left\{ d_j^\circ E_{Y_{|\theta}^\circ} \left[\text{vec}(\widehat{\beta}_j - \beta_j^*)' \left\{ (\Sigma_j^\circ)^{-1} \otimes (X_j^\circ)' X_j^\circ \right\} \text{vec}(\widehat{\beta}_j - \beta_j^*) \right] \right\} \\
 &= \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \{ d_j^\circ p_j^\circ m \} \tag{12}
 \end{aligned}$$

Because $\text{vec}(\widehat{\beta}_j - \beta_j^*)' \left\{ (\Sigma_j^\circ)^{-1} \otimes (X_j^\circ)' X_j^\circ \right\} \text{vec}(\widehat{\beta}_j - \beta_j^*) \sim \chi_{p_j^\circ m}^2$ (Edward et al., 1994) [6]

where $\text{vec}(\widehat{\beta}_j - \beta_j^*)$ is the vector of dimension $p_j^\circ m$ obtained by stacking the columns of the matrix $(\widehat{\beta}_j - \beta_j^*)$ and \otimes is the Kronecker product.

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{Y|\theta^\circ} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \text{tr}(W_j^\circ) \text{tr}(\hat{\Sigma}_j^{-1} \Sigma_j^\circ) \right\} &\approx \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \text{tr}(W_j^\circ) d_j^\circ \text{tr}[(\Sigma_j^\circ)^{-1} \Sigma_j^\circ] \\
 &= \sum_{j=1}^{k^\circ} \text{tr}(W_j^\circ) d_j^\circ m
 \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

We replace the results (12) and (13) in (11) after we replace k° and W_j° by k and \widehat{W}_j respectively. (Naik et al., 2007) [12].

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{Y|\theta^\circ} \left\{ E_{Y|\theta^\circ} \left\{ -2L_c(\hat{\phi}(Y), \hat{t}(Y), Y^*, X) \right\} \right\} &\approx E_{Y|\theta^\circ} \left\{ -2 \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{n}_j \log \hat{\alpha}_j + nm \log(2\pi) \right. \\
 &\left. + \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{n}_j \log(\det(\hat{\Sigma}_j)) \right\} + \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{d}_j m p_j + \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{d}_j m \hat{n}_j
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Finally, we base the model order estimation on the minimization of

$$-2 \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{n}_j \log \hat{\alpha}_j + nm \log(2\pi) + \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{n}_j \log(\det(\hat{\Sigma}_j)) + \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{d}_j m p_j + \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{d}_j m \hat{n}_j$$

Ignoring the term does not depend on the order (k, p) , we obtain the criterion for estimating the order of the multivariate gaussian regression mixture model

$$MRC_v(k, p) = \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{n}_j \log(\det(\hat{\Sigma}_j)) + \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{d}_j m (p_j + \hat{n}_j) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{n}_j \log(\hat{\alpha}_j) \tag{15}$$

where $p = (p_1, \dots, p_k)$, $\hat{n}_j = \text{tr}(\widehat{W}_j)$, $p_j = \text{tr}(\widehat{H}_j)$ and $\hat{d}_j = \frac{\hat{n}_j}{\hat{n}_j - (m + p_j + 1)}$

and we have

$$(\hat{k}, \hat{p}) = \underset{1 \leq k \leq K, 1 \leq p_1, \dots, p_k \leq P}{\text{argmin}} \{MRC_v(k, p)\}$$

where K and P are sufficiently large such that $K \geq k^\circ$ and $P \geq \max\{p_j^\circ, j = 1, \dots, k^\circ\}$.

3.3. Remarks

- $m = 1$ (univariate case)

$$MRC_v(k, p) = \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{n}_j \log(\hat{\sigma}_j^2) + \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{n}_j \frac{(\hat{n}_j + p_j)}{(\hat{n}_j - p_j - 2)} - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{n}_j \log(\hat{\alpha}_j) = MRC(k, p)$$

where $p = (p_1, \dots, p_k)$

This is the criterion defined by Naik et al. [12]

- $k = 1$ and $m = 1$ (case of a single component and univariate regression)

$$MRC_v(1, p) = n \log(\hat{\sigma}^2) + \frac{n(n+p)}{n-p-2} = AIC_c(p)$$

We obtain the corrected Akaike criterion proposed by Hurvich et al. [7]

- $k = 1$ (case of a single component and multivariate regression)

$$MRC_v(1, p) = n \log(\hat{\Sigma}) + dm(p+n) = AIC_c(p)$$

where $d = \frac{n}{n-(m+p+1)}$

We obtain the corrected Akaike criterion proposed by Edward et al. [6]

4. Simulation

We apply the criterion MRC_v to simulated data from multivariate gaussian mixture regression models with the same covariates across components ($p_1 = \dots = p_k = p$) and compare the results obtained with those of the criteria AIC and BIC .

Selection procedure:

To simultaneously determine the number of components and explanatory variables for multivariate gaussian mixture regression models, we use the following procedure.

For the given $\{(k, p): k = 1, \dots, K, p = 1, \dots, P\}$

1. We use the K-means algorithm (MacQueen et al., 1967) [10] to classify the observations of a candidate matrix X into k groups so that the initial probabilities $\tau_{ij}^{(e)}$ can be estimated to initialize the EM algorithm.
2. We apply the EM algorithm to estimate the parameters of the multivariate mixture regression model
3. We calculate the MRC_v , AIC , and BIC

$$MRC_v(k, p) = \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{n}_j \log(\det(\hat{\Sigma}_j)) + \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{d}_j m(p + \hat{n}_j) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{n}_j \log(\hat{\alpha}_j)$$

$$AIC(k, p) = -2L(\hat{\phi}, Y, X) + 2u(k, p)$$

$$BIC(k, p) = -2L(\hat{\phi}, Y, X) + \log(n)u(k, p)$$

$u(k, p)$ is the number of free parameters of multivariate regression mixture model

$$u(k, p) = (k - 1) + kpm + km(m + 1)/2$$

4. The orders estimated by these criteria are:

$$(\hat{k}, \hat{p}) = \underset{1 \leq k \leq K, 1 \leq p \leq P}{\operatorname{argmin}} \{MRC_v(k, p)\}$$

$$(\hat{k}, \hat{p}) = \underset{1 \leq k \leq K, 1 \leq p \leq P}{\operatorname{argmin}} \{AIC(k, p)\}$$

$$(\hat{k}, \hat{p}) = \underset{1 \leq k \leq K, 1 \leq p \leq P}{\operatorname{argmin}} \{BIC(k, p)\}$$

• **Example 1:** We consider a multivariate gaussian mixture regression model with dimension ($m = 2$), and the true number of components ($k^\circ = 2$), each component has a multivariate regression model with three explanatory variables ($p^\circ = 3$), the response variable of each component is generated from $Y_j = X_j^\circ \beta_j^\circ + \epsilon_j^\circ$, ($j = 1, 2$), where:

- The elements of the $n_1 \times 3$ matrix X_1° and the $n_2 \times 3$ matrix X_2° are generated from the uniform distributions $U(0,5)$ and $U(5,10)$ respectively
- The true regression parameters are $\beta_1^\circ = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$, $\beta_2^\circ = \begin{pmatrix} 6 & 6 \\ 7 & 7 \\ 8 & 8 \end{pmatrix}$
- The rows of the error matrix ϵ_j° are assumed to be independent with identical $\mathcal{N}_2(0, I_2)$ distributions ($j = 1, 2$)

We consider 100 samples generated from the true model, of size $n = n_1 + n_2 = 30$

and $n = n_1 + n_2 = 60$.

We consider seven candidate regression models ($P = 7$) stored in a $n_j \times 7$ matrix X_j in each of the two components. The first three columns of X_j ($j = 1, 2$) are the same as X_j° while the last four columns are generated from $U(0,5)$ and $U(10,15)$ for X_1 and X_2 respectively. The observed matrix X is obtained by stacking X_1 and X_2 one on top of the other. Similarly, using the same method with Y_1 and Y_2 , we construct the observed dependent variable Y .

We consider five sets of candidate components ($K = 5$). Hence, we have 35 possibilities, seven nested regression models in each of the five sets of candidate components. For each sample, we calculate the selection criteria MRC_v , AIC , and BIC according to the selection procedure described below. The results are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Order frequencies estimated on 100 samples ($k^\circ = 2, p^\circ = 3$), $n_1 = n_2 = 15$

Criteria	MRC_p							BIC							AIC						
	1	2	$p^\circ = 3$	4	5	6	7	1	2	$p^\circ = 3$	4	5	6	7	1	2	$p^\circ = 3$	4	5	6	7
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
$k^\circ = 2$	0	0	97	2	0	0	0	71	1	0	0	0	0	19	2	4	4	0	0	0	
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	5	0	
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	2	15	0	0	
5	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	4	18	0	0	0	3	16	29	0	0	

Table 2: Order frequencies estimated on 100 samples ($k^\circ = 2, p^\circ = 3$), $n_1 = n_2 = 30$

Criteria	MRC_p							BIC							AIC						
	1	2	$p^\circ = 3$	4	5	6	7	1	2	$p^\circ = 3$	4	5	6	7	1	2	$p^\circ = 3$	4	5	6	7
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
$k^\circ = 2$	0	0	99	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	85	8	4	1	1	0	0	
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
5	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

• **Example 2:** The true model is a multivariate gaussian mixture regression model with dimension ($m = 2$), and three components ($k^\circ = 3$), each component has a multivariate regression model with four explanatory variables ($p^\circ = 4$), the response variable of each component is generated from $Y_j = X_j^\circ \beta_j^\circ + \epsilon_j^\circ$, ($j = 1, 2, 3$) where:

- The elements of the $n_1 \times 4$ matrix X_1° , the $n_2 \times 4$ matrix X_2° and the $n_3 \times 4$ matrix X_3° are generated from the uniform distributions $U(0,5)$, $U(5,10)$ and $U(10,15)$ respectively

- The true regression parameters are $\beta_1^\circ = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$, $\beta_2^\circ = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 2 & 2 \\ 3 & 3 \\ 4 & 4 \end{pmatrix}$ and $\beta_3^\circ = \begin{pmatrix} 5 & 5 \\ 6 & 6 \\ 7 & 7 \\ 8 & 8 \end{pmatrix}$

- The rows of the error matrix ϵ_j° are assumed to be independent, with identical $\mathcal{N}_2(0, I_2)$ distributions ($j = 1, 2, 3$)

We consider 100 samples generated from the true model, of size $n = n_1 + n_2 + n_3 = 30$ and $n = n_1 + n_2 + n_3 = 90$. We consider seven candidate regression models ($P = 7$) stored in a $n_j \times 7$ matrix X_j in each of the three components. The first four columns

of X_j ($j = 1, 2, 3$) are the same as X_j° while the last three columns are generated from $U(0,5)$, $U(5,10)$ and $U(10,15)$ for X_1 , X_2 and X_3 respectively. The observed matrix X is obtained by stacking X_1 , X_2 , and X_3 one on top of the other. Similarly, using the same method with Y_1 , Y_2 , and Y_3 , we construct the observed dependent variable Y . We consider five sets of candidate components ($K = 5$). The results are summarized in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3: Order frequencies estimated on 100 samples ($k^\circ = 3$, $p^\circ = 4$), $n_1 = n_2 = n_3 = 10$

Criteria	MRC_v							BIC							AIC						
	1	2	3	$p^\circ = 4$	5	6	7	1	2	3	$p^\circ = 4$	5	6	7	1	2	3	$p^\circ = 4$	5	6	7
1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	2	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
$k^\circ = 3$	0	0	0	90	0	0	0	0	0	0	61	7	1	13	0	0	0	14	2	6	18
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	1	6	12
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	4	6	0	0	0	1	5	13	22

Table 4: Order frequencies estimated on 100 samples ($k^\circ = 3$, $p^\circ = 4$), $n_1 = n_2 = n_3 = 30$

Criteria	MRC_v							BIC							AIC						
	1	2	3	$p^\circ = 4$	5	6	7	1	2	3	$p^\circ = 4$	5	6	7	1	2	3	$p^\circ = 4$	5	6	7
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
$k^\circ = 3$	0	0	0	94	6	0	0	0	0	0	94	6	0	0	0	0	0	83	11	3	3
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

In view of the results, whether for mixture models of two or three distributions, the criterion MRC_v is clearly better than both the criteria AIC and BIC for small samples, in Table 3. for example, with $n = 30$, the percentage of good selection is 90% with MRC_v , 61% and 14% with BIC and AIC respectively. For large samples, the criteria MRC_v and BIC have the same performance, in Table 2. for example, with $n = 60$, the percentage of good selection is 99% with MRC_v and 100% with BIC . We also observe that the criterion AIC is much less performant than the criteria BIC and MRC_v for both small and large samples.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we derived the criterion MRC_v for the joint selection of the number of components and variables for multivariate gaussian mixture regression models, which is based on the log-likelihood and the Kullback asymmetric divergence. We compared our

criterion MRC_v with the criteria AIC and BIC on simulated data from multivariate gaussian mixture regression models for small and large samples. The numerical results show that the criterion MRC_v outperforms the criteria AIC and BIC for small samples and has the same performance as the criterion BIC for large samples. Therefore, we suggest using in an application the criterion MRC_v against the criteria AIC and BIC .

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